

Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System

Model-based quantification of fluxes between shelf seas

Deliverable D1.8

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Table of contents

1. Publishable summary.....	4
2. Work performed and main achievements.....	4
2.1 Description of the work performed.....	4
2.1.1 Model Description and Experiments.....	4
2.1.2 Transport across sections.....	5
2.1.3 Sensitivity experiments.....	11
2.2 References.....	16
2.3 Open Science.....	17
3. Results.....	18
4. Impact.....	18

1. Publishable summary

The Antarctic marginal seas are interconnected through generally westward flowing current systems such as the Antarctic Slope Current (ASC, Thompson et al. 2018) and the Antarctic Coastal Current (ACoC) along the continental slope and coast, respectively. The ASC is a quasi-circumpolar feature that starts in the Bellingshausen Sea and vanishes near the tip of the Antarctic Peninsula in the Weddell Sea, and is most pronounced along the East Antarctic continental slope downstream of the Ross Sea. The ASC transports various water masses, such as surface waters, Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW, $>0^{\circ}\text{C}$), and newly formed Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW), and can thus impact hydrographic conditions and processes in neighboring subregions by advecting hydrographic anomalies. In this deliverable, we quantify fluxes between different Antarctic subregions and assess their downstream impact based on output from the Finite volume Sea Ice-Ocean Model (FESOM2).

We used FESOM2 to quantify the transport on the continental shelf and slope (Fig. 1) and find that the net exchange is much larger on the slope. The transport was split into three water masses, namely Surface Water (SW), Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), and AABW. A more in-depth analysis was carried out for along-slope transports of AABW across boundaries between different Antarctic shelf seas.

The model was able to reproduce the dominant source regions of AABW in the Weddell and Ross Seas, as well as the minor contributions from Prydz Bay and Cape Darnley (Cooperation Sea), and Adélie Coast (Dumont D'Urville Sea). The average AABW transport agrees well with earlier estimates for the Weddell Sea (4 Sverdrup (Sv), $1 \text{ Sv} = 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), and is slightly higher (2.6 vs 1.7 Sv) in the Ross Sea. The mean AABW transport along the Adélie Coast slope is negligible, while on the Cooperation Sea the transport is 0.2 Sv and smaller than earlier estimates, although observations (0.7-1.5 Sv) are highly variable and seasonally biased (Purkey et al 2017). A strong seasonality of AABW export was present in all formation sites and thus in agreement with earlier findings (Purkey et al 2017).

To assess the role of ice shelf melt on downstream hydrographic conditions and water mass formation, we performed various sensitivity experiments by varying the level of meltwater. Shutting off glacial melt upstream of the major dense water formation sites increases the final salinity of the AABW, with a larger impact on the simulated AABW volume in those regions where less bottom water is formed. The experiments indicate that while glacial melt does affect the water mass structure downstream, it has only a little impact on the melting of downstream ice shelves.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

2.1.1 Model Description and Experiments

“The Finite volume Sea Ice-Ocean Model (FESOM2) is a multi-resolution ocean general circulation model that solves the equations of motion describing the ocean and sea ice using finite-volume methods on unstructured computational grids. The model is developed and operated by the Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research (AWI), in Bremerhaven, Germany.” (quoted from the FESOM2 documentation, <https://fesom2.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>, Danilov et al. 2017, Danilov et al. 2015). The interaction with the ice shelf is based on the three-equation approach proposed by Hellmer and Olbers (1989). The fresh water input related to ice shelf melt and the water freezing is handled as a virtual salt flux. Heat and freshwater fluxes are applied only to the layers in direct contact with the ice shelf base.

We performed a reference simulation for the period 1958 to 2020 with forcing data derived from the Japanese 55-year Reanalysis, or JRA-55 (Kobayashi et al. 2015, Harada et al. 2016). Furthermore, three sensitivity experiments were conducted to investigate how the GMW originating upstream from three AABW formation sites, namely Ross Sea, Prydz Bay, and Southern Weddell Sea, affect the dense water production. In the first experiment, all the temperature and salinity changes associated with the ice shelves in the Bellingshausen and Amundsen Seas (Fig. 1), hereafter referred to as BeAm experiment, are set to 0 and the cavities are treated as caves where the water can circulate but is not affected by the environment. In the second experiment, we shut down the ice shelves between 80° E and 105° E (Fig. 1), West and Shackleton Ice Shelf (WeSh experiment). For the third experiment, the ice shelves on the eastern Weddell Sea between 29° W and 9.5° E are turned off, EWS experiment; the affected ice shelves are Brunt, Riiser-Larsen, Ekstrom and Fimbul. The experiments branch out from the reference run in 1991 and run until 2020, all model outputs are given in monthly means.

To gain an overview over the ACoC and ASC transports around Antarctica, we defined 10 sections going from the coast towards the open ocean and ending at the 3000 m isobath (Fig. 1). The sections are divided into continental shelf (red) and slope (black) parts and named by their geographical positions (magenta text next to the sections). The transport was also split into water masses fractions; based on the model climatology (van Caspel et al. 2024) we defined surface waters (SW) as lighter than 1028 kg/m³, denser waters are accounted as CDW if they have potential temperature (PT) larger than 0.1 °C, or AABW if they are colder than this threshold. We chose a slightly higher temperature than the typically used 0 °C to account for the warm model bias on the continental slope. Following the main current direction, positive values are used for westward/northward transport. All mean transport values are presented in Fig.1 and in Table 1; the transport time series from each section are in Fig. 2. Besides net transport we also calculate the potential temperature (PT) and salinity of each water mass with volume larger than +0.1 Sverdrup (Sv) (1 Sv = 10⁶ m³ s⁻¹). The properties are weighted according to the volume passing through each cell.

2.1.2 Transport across sections

The average westward transport is small in the Bellingshausen Sea, the region where the ASC starts: 1.6 Sv flow through the slope of section 102W and 0.2 Sv on the continental shelf. Only SW and CDW are carried from the Bellingshausen into the Amundsen Sea. Between section 102W and 140W, the SW gets colder, average PT decreases from 0.72 °C to -0.2°C, and fresher, S changes from 34.532 to 34.23. The properties of the CDW show only a small variation, PT rises from 0.56 °C to 0.58 °C and S from 34.693 to 34.696. These differences indicate that most of the GMW coming from the Amundsen Sea end up in the SW. With occasional inversions in the direction of the net transport, the ASC is not a permanent feature in this region (Fig. 2).

After leaving the Ross Sea, at section 170E, the ASC carries 7.4 Sv, which split into 1.3 Sv of SW, 3.4 Sv of CDW, and 2.6 Sv of AABW formed in the Ross Sea. The SW and CDW leaving the Ross Sea towards eastern Antarctica are colder than when they enter this basin. The net transport of the ACoC is 0.6 Sv and half of it corresponds to AABW.

Fig. 2: Net transport of the Antarctic Slope Current (ASC), top. Monthly means of the ASC net transport, middle. Net transport of the ASC with the monthly mean subtracted. Each line corresponds to a section and the legend is on the middle figure.

The pulses of AABW formed in Adélie Land are carried towards Mawson Sea (section 113E) together with 3.4 Sv of SW and 9.3 Sv of CDW, both water masses are warmer and saltier than when they leave Ross Sea. No AABW gets to section 113E, and the ASC carries 4.4 Sv of colder and fresher SW and 8.4 Sv of CDW with almost the same average properties as the CDW from the previous section. The CDW mean thermohaline properties remain unchanged as 5.6 Sv of this water mass leave the Cooperation Sea, the next site where AABW is formed. The ASC transports 0.2 Sv of AABW out of this sea (section 60E), and again, all AABW leaves the slope before getting to the next formation area, the southern Weddell Sea.

As it flows towards the Weddell Sea, the ASC carries 5 Sv of CDW across the Prime meridian and 5.2 Sv just before reaching the DSW formation site west of the 28W section. On its transit, the CDW gets warmer and fresher, reaching a PT of 0.47 °C and S 34.677 at section 28W. On average, 3.8 Sv of AABW, PT -0.21 °C and S 34.643, are exported from the southern Weddell Sea. Part of the heat carried by the CDW is lost between section 28W and 70S, PT of 0.28 °C, with minimal changes to its salinity, S 34.674. When the ASC reaches the tip of the Antarctic Peninsula, it transports 4.2 Sv of AABW, but the higher temperature and salinity, PT -0.04 °C and S 34.653, indicate that the increase is due to further mixing with CDW rather than a formation site on the eastern Antarctic Peninsula.

Fig. 3: Time series of AABW net transport on the slope, top, potential temperature, middle, and salinity, bottom.

Overall, the ASC transport has a strong seasonal cycle (Fig. 2, middle) with stronger currents in autumn, which is consistent with the literature (Armitage et al., 2018 in Thompson et al. 2018). There is no time lag between the different regions, which supports the idea that this variability is imprinted by atmospheric forcing, and that advective processes are much less relevant on a seasonal time scale. Removing the monthly climatology from the transport time series (Fig. 2, bottom) shows a variability of ~ 10 Sv (-5 Sv to $+5$ Sv) in most sections, which illustrates how complex this system is. Based on the correlation between the deseasonalized transport (Fig. 2), we can divide the circumpolar seas into subgroups. Depending on the criteria used to divide the area, different subgroups can be proposed. Using a minimum correlation of 0.6 to the center results in 3 blocks connected at their borders, the Amundsen-Ross block (sections 102W to 170E), the eastern Antarctica block (sections 170E to 60E), and the extended Weddell Sea area (sections 60E to 65S). This subdivision into blocks can be beneficial for future studies aimed at understanding the variations within each block.

The monthly AABW transport is also stronger in autumn in sections 170E, 65S, and 70S (not shown). In these sections, the AABW transport is strongly influenced by the ASC strength due to the larger distance to the formation areas. The section at 60E is closer to the formation area, and the transport increases from winter towards the end of spring.

Fig. 4: Time series of AABW net transport on the continental shelf, top, potential temperature, middle, and salinity, bottom.

A strong interannual variability is found in all areas where AABW is observed. All four main formation sites of AABW are present in the model and the volume estimates are close to the values from the literature, especially if the strong interannual variability present in the model and the sparse sampling for most of the observations are taken into account. Moreover, in the model and observations, the largest AABW contribution originates from the Weddell Sea, followed by Ross Sea and the Cooperation Sea, with only sporadic contributions from the Dumont D'Urville Sea.

In agreement with observations, the average AABW that leaves the Ross Sea is saltier than that from the Weddell Sea continental slope, however, it is also colder, which is inconsistent with the literature (e.g. Purkey et al, 2018). In the model, a freshening of the Ross AABW is observed between 2007 and 2012 with recovery after 2016. These changes are associated with a smaller transport of AABW on the slope. Fluctuations in the basal melt of the ice shelves in the Bellingshausen and Amundsen Sea precede the salinity changes in the Ross AABW with stronger melt between 2002 and 2008 (Fig. 6). Model and observation studies link salinity changes on the Ross Sea continental shelf with the basal melt upstream (e.g. Jacobs et al. 2022, Nakayama et al. 2014). A salinity rebound in 2016 was observed near the Ross Ice Shelf (Jacobs et al. 2022).

Table 1: Mean net transport (Vol, in Sv) through each Section. The total transport (Mean Vol) on the continental shelf (ACoC) and on the slope (ASC) is provided as well as the transport from surface waters (SW), Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW) and Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW) on the slope. The mean potential temperature (PT, in °C) and salinity (S) of each water mass are also given.

Section	Mean Vol		SW - ASC			CDW – ASC			AABW - ASC		
	ACoC	ASC	Vol	PT	S	Vol	PT	S	Vol	PT	S
102W	0.2	1.6	0.1	0.72	34.532	1.5	0.56	34.693	0.0		
140W	0.1	1.2	0.3	-0.02	34.323	1.0	0.58	34.696	0.0		
170E	0.6	7.4	1.3	-0.80	34.389	3.4	0.3	34.677	2.6	-0.22	34.653
140E	3	12.8	3.4	-0.05	34.481	9.3	0.34	34.682	0.0	-0.05	34.624
113E	0.6	12.9	4.4	-0.34	34.430	8.4	0.4	34.685	0.0		
60E	0.9	9.2	3.3	-0.68	34.477	5.6	0.39	34.685	0.2	-0.05	34.625
Prime	0.2	9.4	4.4	-0.69	34.393	5.0	0.46	34.686	0.0		
28W	0.1	9.4	4.2	-0.74	34.426	5.2	0.47	34.677	0.0		
70S	0.4	11.7	2.6	-0.99	34.451	5.2	0.28	34.674	3.8	-0.21	34.643
65S	0.3	14.2	3.5	-0.82	34.438	6.5	0.24	34.670	4.2	-0.04	34.653

Fig. 5: Correlation between deseasonalized time series of the Antarctic Slope Current transport for various sections. Section names are on the left and bottom, the numbers and the colours refer to the correlation values.

2.1.3 Sensitivity experiments

In this section, we analyse results from the three sensitivity experiments in which melt rates for three clusters of ice shelves, each located upstream from a known bottom water formation region, are set to zero.

2.1.3.1 Ice shelves in the Bellingshausen and Amundsen Sea (experiment BeAm)

The average melt of all Bellingshausen and Amundsen Sea ice shelves is 910.78 Gt/year in the reference run. A seasonal cycle with stronger melt in summer is superimposed over the interannual variability (Fig. 6). If this large volume of freshwater is not added to the system (experiment BeAm), the average volume of AABW leaving Ross Sea (section 170E) is increased by only 0.01 Sv (from 2.59 Sv to 2.60 Sv). However, the water is saltier, mean $S = 34.673$, and warmer, mean $PT = -0.13$ °C, than in the reference run with $S = 34.653$ and $PT = -0.22$ °C (Fig. 7). The salinity difference increases over the first ten years and is stable between 2000 and 2007 (green line in the Salinity panel of Fig. 7). The freshening trend known from the reference simulation is also present in this sensitivity experiment, which indicates that it is not primarily driven by the ice shelf basal melt upstream. In the first 10 years of the experiment (1991-2000), the average AABW volume is 0.16 Sv smaller, 0.08 °C warmer, and the salinity is 0.012 higher. In the second decade, the volume is 0.16 Sv larger, 0.12 °C warmer, and the salinity difference is 0.022. In the third decade, the AABW transport is only 0.04 Sv larger with a temperature and salinity difference of 0.09°C and 0.024.

In contrast to their effects on the AABW leaving the Ross Sea, the impact of ice shelf meltwater fluxes from the Bellingshausen and Amundsen Seas on Ross Ice Shelf melting is small. Ross Ice Shelf melt during winter months is around 50 Gt per year with small interannual variability, the maximum melt in summer varies between 100 and 250 Gt per year (Fig. 6). The average melt increases from 83 Gt/year in the reference simulation to 88 Gt/year in the BeAm experiment.

Following the path of the continental slope circulation westward, the absence of the melt water from the Bellingshausen and Amundsen Sea increases the average AABW formation rate off Adelie coast (section 140E, Fig. 8) to 0.17 Sv with a strong seasonal cycle that feature peak formation rates exceeding 0.5 Sv in winter and early spring. Mean salinity and PT change to 34.630 and -0.09 °C. In most cases, the changes are caused by the intensification of pulses of AABW that are also present in the reference run, but there are also several new pulses. The first noticeable difference is in 1994, but from the winter of 1996 until the end of the simulation, 2020, AABW is present on the slope in all the winters. On average, the PT is 0.07 °C lower in the BeAm experiment than in the reference run and the salinity difference is 0.011.

Even in the Cooperation Sea, the region off Amery Ice Shelf, the effect of the GMW from the Bellingshausen and Amundsen Sea is still visible. Differences between the BeAm experiment and the reference simulation start to increase from the third year of simulation (1993) onwards; the difference is subject to interannual fluctuations, but it continues to increase until 2015 (Fig. 9). The AABW formed in the absence of GMW is colder, and the difference fluctuates in synchrony with the volume changes; the mean PT difference is -0.08°C. The salinity difference increases over time in the BeAm experiment; the AABW is 0.002 saltier on average.

Despite the increased volume of AABW leaving the Cooperation Sea, the perturbation caused in the BeAm experiment does not reach the Weddell Sea. The simulated melt of the Eastern Weddell ice shelves (Fig. 6) sums up to 108 Gt/year on average; the summer melt goes up to 360 Gt/year, while during the colder months it is around 48 Sv. In the southern Weddell Sea, the Filchner-Ronne Ice Shelf mean basal melt amounts to 89 Gt/year, the minimum melt during the colder months varies between 60 and 80 Gt/year,

while the maximum melt rate in summer ranges from 90 to 140 Gt/year. None of these melt rates is affected by the removal of Bellingshausen/Amundsen Sea GMW, nor by any other of the ice shelf clusters addressed (see below). However, we find a steady increase in AABW salinity at the cross-slope section at 70°S from 1994 to 2016 in the BeAm experiment (Fig. 10), and in the last 4 years of simulation, 2016 to 2020, the transport of AABW increases by approximately 0.5 Sv. The differences in a cross-slope section at 65 °S (not shown) are very similar to the changes at 70 °S.

2.1.3.2 West and Shackleton Ice shelves (experiment WeSh)

Compared to the meltwater fluxes from the Bellingshausen and Amundsen Seas, the freshwater input from the West and Shackleton ice shelves, upstream from Amery Ice Shelf, is much smaller. The combined melting of West and Shackleton ice shelves oscillates between 300 Gt/year during summer and 20 Gt/year during winter months, with an average melt of 93 Gt/year. The Amery Ice Shelf mean basal melt is 58 Gt/year, fluctuating between 30 Gt/year and 140 Gt/year. Neither of these melt rates is substantially affected by freshwater input from any of the other ice shelves.

The effect of the subtraction of GMW from West and Shackleton ice shelves, the WeSh experiment, on the volume of AABW on the Cooperation Sea continental slope starts in the first winter of the experiment, 1991, and increases every winter until 1995. After that, the difference is only subject to interannual variability. Similar to the BeAm experiment, the AABW in WeSh is colder than in the reference simulation, but the PT and salinity differences are only -0.04 °C and -0.0003, respectively, and thus smaller than for the far-away located but heavily melting Bellingshausen/Amundsen Sea ice shelves (Fig. 9).

While not very large in amplitude, a signature of the perturbation imposed in the WeSh experiment can still be found in the AABW outflow from the Weddell Sea at 70°S (Fig. 10). The response is very similar to that in the EWS experiment (see below).

2.1.3.3 Eastern Weddell Sea ice shelves (experiment EWS)

Like for the West and Shackleton ice shelves, meltwater fluxes from the Eastern Weddell Ice Shelves, located upstream from Filchner-Ronne Ice Shelf and the bottom water formation sites of the Weddell Sea, are much smaller than the contribution from the Bellingshausen/Amundsen Sea ice shelves. None of the ice shelves analysed here, not even the neighbouring Filchner-Ronne Ice Shelf, shows any response in basal melt rates if GMW from the Eastern Weddell Ice Shelves is removed (Fig. 6).

However, compared to the reference simulation, the volume of AABW crossing 70 °S at the eastern coast of the Antarctic Peninsula in the Weddell Sea does show small differences throughout the whole period without GMW input from the eastern Weddell Sea (Fig. 10). With occasional pulses of larger AABW flow, the mean increase is by 0.1 Sv, the PT difference is negligible and the average salinity increase is of 0.001. The effects are very similar to those in the WeSh experiment and, despite the larger distance of the West and Shackleton ice shelves, are often seen in synchrony between the two experiments, indicating that the timing of events is determined by local or regional processes, likely related to atmospheric variability, rather than by a teleconnection to ice shelves in other sectors of the Southern Ocean.

Fig. 6: Simulated basal melt of major ice shelves around the Antarctic continent in the reference simulation and the three sensitivity experiments. Some of the lines overlap due to the very small differences. The lines indicating zero melt rates for the ice shelves, which have been switched off in the sensitivity experiments, have been omitted to allow for a better resolution of seasonal and interannual variability in the plots.

Fig. 7: Time series of AABW transport (top), potential temperature (middle) and salinity (bottom) differences between the sensitivity experiments and the reference simulation on section 170E, directly west of the Ross Sea. The Bellingshausen Amundsen (BeAm) experiment is shown in green, the West and Shackleton (WeSh) experiment in red and the eastern Weddell Sea experiment in magenta. Note that the y axes are different on Figs. 7 to 10.

Fig. 8: Time series of AABW transport (top), potential temperature (middle) and salinity (bottom) differences between the sensitivity experiments and the reference simulation on section 140E off Adélie coast. The Bellingshausen Amundsen (BeAm) experiment is shown in green, the West and Shackleton (WeSh) experiment in red and the eastern Weddell Sea experiment in magenta.

Fig. 9: Time series of AABW transport (top), potential temperature (middle) and salinity (bottom) differences between the sensitivity experiments and the reference simulation on section 60E at the transition between Cooperation Sea and Cosmonaut Sea, i.e. west of Amery Ice Shelf. The Bellingshausen Amundsen (BeAm) experiment is shown in green, the West and Shackleton (WeSh) experiment in red and the eastern Weddell Sea experiment in magenta.

2.1.3.4 Summary

Two of our findings seem particularly noteworthy to us. First, our results indicate that the preconditioning of water masses upstream from the “classical” AABW formation sites off Ross, Amery, and Filchner-Ronne ice shelves has little or no effect on the melt rates of these larger ice shelves, but still affects the AABW formation rate and properties. As a general pattern, the removal of glacial meltwater increases bottom water formation rates and bottom water salinity downstream. For temperature, the response is less consistent: While the AABW leaving the Ross Sea becomes warmer when the GMW flow from upstream is removed, we find a cooling of the bottom water produced along the East Antarctic coast in this case. For the Weddell Sea, the temperature response of the AABW is inconsistent and seems to depend on the source region of the GMW. We hypothesise that the colder and saltier bottom water along the East Antarctic coast results from enhanced DSW formation, which starts from saltier surface water in the case of less GMW. When the newly formed bottom water travels down the slope, it keeps a stronger signal of the DSW, thus the mean potential temperature of the AABW is lower. In the Ross Sea, where the DSW production is already large, the effects of increased DSW formation are surpassed by the changes to the CDW, which mixes with the DSW to form AABW. With the removal of GMW the CDW gets warmer and saltier, and so does the newly formed AABW.

Also noteworthy is the long reach of the GMW from Bellingshausen and Amundsen Seas. On the one hand, this can be attributed to the fact that this cluster yields by far the largest contribution of GMW. On the other hand, it also points to the Antarctic Slope Current providing coherent transport on a circumpolar scale.

While it is plausible to assume that transport with the ASC is by advection, so that propagation of any perturbation should adhere to the advective time scale (about 27 years for a full circumpolar loop according to model simulations by Beckmann and Timmermann, 2001), we find that a signature originating from removing the Bellingshausen/Amundsen freshwater source arrives in the Weddell Sea after only four to five years. Our hypothesis is that through a modified density field, transport of the ASC is modulated, so that not the meltwater itself but the perturbed current system sheds information towards the Weddell Sea. Fast circumpolar connections generated by waves have been reported before (see the review by Thompson et al.

2020), and a complex interaction between the effects of different types of waves is likely over such large distances. In any case, to our knowledge, the effects of far away sources on AABW formation were shown here for the first time, although its existence was speculated on before. The correlation table presented in Fig. 5 supports the idea that, although it can be divided into subregions, the circumpolar ASC system is formed by interconnected blocks. A detailed investigation of the relevant mechanisms will be performed at a later stage.

Fig. 10: Time series of AABW transport (top), potential temperature (middle) and salinity (bottom) differences between the sensitivity experiments and the reference simulation on section 70S on the eastern side of the Antarctic Peninsula. The Bellingshausen Amundsen (BeAm) experiment is shown in green, the West and Shackleton (WeSh) experiment in red and the eastern Weddell Sea (EWS) experiment in magenta.

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2.3 Open Science

The model results used in this study are freely available from Zenodo, see the summary table below.

Simulation	Variables	DOIs link
Circumpolar Simulation Reference Run	PT and S	https://zenodo.org/records/15189061
Circumpolar Simulation Reference Run	U and V	https://zenodo.org/records/15280675
Bellingshausen and Amundsen Seas Experiment (BeAm)	PT and S	https://zenodo.org/records/15267996
BeAm experiment	U and V	https://zenodo.org/records/15299650
West and Shackleton Ice Shelf Experiment (WeSh)	PT and S	https://zenodo.org/records/15268272
WeSh experiment	U and V	https://zenodo.org/records/15299425
Eastern Weddell Sea Experiment (EWS)	PT and S	https://zenodo.org/records/15268317
EWS experiment	U and V	https://zenodo.org/records/15299705

All knowledge gained will be published in an open-access format.

The results presented in this report will be complemented by further analysis and published as a peer-reviewed manuscript in open access.

3. Results

We showed that the model is capable of reproducing the ASC and the export of DSW in a satisfactory way, including a strong seasonal and interannual variability. The experiments designed to study the effect of GMW withdrawal on AABW showed that the volume of freshwater added to the system plays a larger role than the distance to the formation site. Furthermore, the analysis indicates that the circumpolar seas are connected within periods faster than that provided by pure advection, and perturbations in one region propagate very fast around the continent.

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to achieving the project's following objectives, as described in the action description.

O1: Reduce the spatial and knowledge gaps in ocean observations around Antarctica, particularly relating to ice sheet-ocean interaction and deep water formation and export.

This analysis enhanced our understanding of the circumpolar effects of GMW originating from various regions on AABW export. It does so individually for each of the major AABW formation regions.

O5: Assess how global ocean circulation is impacted by freshwater discharge from the northern and southern ice sheets.

We showed how changes in meltwater input from the Antarctic ice shelves can affect the AABW export from their formation sites.